

ROLE AND METHODS OF THE INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

Yakubova Madina Kutfidinovn

International University of Tourism and Cultural Heritage "Silk Road", Senio Lecturee

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Abstract. *The article reveals the importance of developing intercultural communication skills in foreign language classes and analyses various methods of active learning to improve language skills and understanding of the culture of the target language. The article also discusses the effectiveness of modern technologies in language teaching process.*

Keywords: *intercultural communication skills, active learning, foreign language, modern technologies*

Аннотация. *Статья раскрывает важность развитие навыков межкультурного общение на занятиях иностранного языка и анализирует различные методы активного обучения для улучшения языковых способностей и понимания культуры изучаемого языка. Так же статья рассматривает эффективность применения современных технологий в процессе обучения иностранным языкам.*

Ключевые слова: *навыки межкультурного общения, активные обучение, иностранный язык, современные технологии*

Annotasiya. *Ush bu ilmiy maqolada chet tili darolarida madaniyatlararo muloqot ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish muhimligi yoritgan. Bundan tashqari maqolada til qobiliyatlarini yaxshilash va o'rganilayotgan til madaniyatini tushunish uchun turli faol o'rganish usullari tahlil qilinadi. Maqolada chet tillarini o'qitish jarayonida zamonaviy texnologiyalardan foydalanish samaradorligi ham ko'rib chiqiladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *madaniyatlararo muloqot qobiliyatlari, faol o'rganish, chet tili, zamonaviy texnologiyalar*

Özet. *Bu bilimsel makale, yabancı dil derslerinde kültürlerarası iletişim becerilerini geliştirmenin önemini vurgulamaktadır. Ayrıca makale, dil becerilerini geliştirmek ve çalışılan dilin kültürünü anlamak için çeşitli aktif öğrenme yöntemlerini analiz etmektedir. Makalede yabancı dil öğretimi sürecinde modern teknolojilerin kullanılmasının etkinliği de ele alınmaktadır.*

Anahtar kelimeler: *kültürlerarası iletişim becerileri, aktif öğrenme, yabancı dil, modern teknolojiler*

The world today requires from the individual the ability to coexist together, in other words people must be able to build an effective conversation with representatives of other cultures. No doubts that a language plays the most important role, as it is the only possible bridge of mutual understanding and interaction between people with different linguistic and ethno-ethnic background. However, ability to speak a foreign language is not effective without skills of intercultural communication during the interaction of representatives of different cultures. The gap in the knowledge of other culture could cause a "failures" in communication with native speakers.

Therefore, a foreign language teaching in higher education institutions should be aimed at involving students to the process of intercultural communication (ICC). According to Lustig and Koester (2011), "intercultural communication occurs when large and important cultural differences create dissimilar interpretations and expectations about how to communicate

competently" (p.52). So, as any kind of communication, intercultural communication has its own goals, which determines the effectiveness or ineffectiveness of communication.

Furthermore, it is important to understand the concept of "intercultural competence". The notion shows a person's ability to successfully participate in intercultural communication. The effectiveness of communication is equal to the level of mutual understanding among communicators. To achieve mutual understanding all participants of the conversation should have a certain set of common knowledge, skills and abilities, which is named "intercultural competence".

The most complete definition of intercultural competence is formulated by G.V. Elizarova: "Intercultural competence is a competence of a special nature, based on knowledge and skills, the ability which are implemented during intercultural communication by creating a common meaning of what is happening for communicators with the aim of achieving a positive result of communication for both parties. Intercultural competence has no analogy with the communicative competence of native speakers and can be inherent only to a mediator of cultures – an individual who learns a certain language in a particular language in order to achieve a positive result of communication". (p.236). The definition makes it obvious that intercultural competence is an ability that is very complex in its essence and labour-intensive to master.

Darla Dearnorff (2006) gave the following explanation, "Intercultural [communication] competence is the ability to interact effectively and appropriately in intercultural situations, based on specific attitudes, intercultural knowledge, skills and reflection" (p.5). The author presented a pyramid of intercultural communication competence. Her pyramid includes three characteristics, which allow development and excellence of the competence. They are (1) motivation, which based on interest in culture, openness and respect for themselves and others; (2) knowledge, which based on understanding, knowledge of culture and sociolinguistic awareness; (3) skills — possessing certain communication and listening skills such as listening, interpreting, analyzing, and evaluating.

Thus, intercultural competence is an ability that allows an individual to realise himself/herself within the framework of the dialogue of cultures, i.e. in the conditions of intercultural communication. It is a complex formation that includes the following components: attitudes, knowledge and skills, thinking features that relate to both native and learnt cultures. At the same time, the component "attitudes" includes openness to new information, readiness to abandon prejudices, consistent development of tolerance, acceptance, adaptation to the phenomena of foreign language communication.

Nowadays, the practical issues of ICC training are less developed than the theory of ICC. Therefore, the main efforts in language teaching should be directed to:

- formation of students' foreign language communicative competence;
- socialisation of the student by means of a foreign;
- training of communicative behaviour;
- Create basis for communication with representatives of other cultures and formation of receptivity, observation and tolerance;
- multicultural development of a student.

The modern education system has a wide choice of ways to develop students' intercultural competence. The most effective among them are those, which are based on active learning "tasks which requires the analysis of facts in the form of diagnostics of specific situations of intercultural communication and generation of all available knowledge and skills to overcome cultural

misunderstanding. The main elements of active learning are considered to be speaking, listening, reading, writing, and reflection. These elements engage the student in mental activity and allow to clarify, question existing knowledge and learn new knowledge.

For this reason, active forms of training should be more widespread: role-playing games, discussions, case studies, trainings, etc., allowing their participants to immerse themselves in active controlled communication with the cultural aspects. The most productive way in developing intercultural competence is the combination of lectures-presentations and video lectures with practical classes, during which students get an opportunity to experience feelings and emotions arising in real ICC situations.

Modern education requires teachers not only to have profound knowledge, but also to be proficient in modern information technologies. It is essential to implement the whole teaching process on the basis of modern technologies. However, this work is difficult for a number of reasons, among which material support of the educational process is not always the main one. Often teachers themselves are not willing to change and master modern technologies, preferring traditional, "proven" forms of conducting classes.

At Silk Road International University of Tourism and Cultural Heritage all smart facilities are created to create authentic atmosphere of different cultures and successfully solve the following didactic tasks:

- (a) Formation and improvement of all four languages on the basis of materials of different degrees of complexity;
- b) enriching the vocabulary with the vocabulary of a modern foreign language;
- c) familiarisation with various aspects of foreign language culture.

The results of implementation of active learning is based on several factors as: selection of the active form that best suits the given material and the stage of its study; careful planning and organisation of work; creation of a favourable environment in the group (informal conversation, joking, the teacher's body language is important); use of technical means (projector, audio recording, video camera, computer class); variety of methods and forms of active learning used, combining them with traditional ones and etc.

The effectiveness of the development of students' intercultural competence depends on the construction of the educational process taking into account the interests and needs of the modern student, the mandatory use of authentic materials (printed, audio and video materials), periodic control of the level of intercultural competence on the basis of testing, writing a creative essay, defence of projects, creation of portfolios, etc., as well as the development of intercultural competence(4, p. 118).

The teacher's personality is of great importance in this regard: high level of foreign language communicative competence, open-mindedness, openness, experience of intercultural communication. Thus, the development of intercultural competence of students is an urgent need of today and the correct construction of this process will largely depend on its result - readiness and ability of the individual to dialogue of cultures.

REFERENCES

1. Deardorff, D. K. (2006). Identification and assessment of intercultural competence as a student outcome of Internationalization. *Journal of Studies in International Education*, 10(3), 241–266. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1028315306287002>
2. Elizarova G.V. *Culture and Teaching Foreign Languages*. St.P., 2005. 236 p.

3. Lustig, M. W., & Koester, J. (2017). *Intercultural Competence Interpersonal Communication Across Cultures* (7th ed.). Pearson.
4. Yakubova, M. (2021). Intercultural Communication and Language Varieties of the English Language. *International Journal of World Languages*, 1(2). Retrieved from <https://www.ejournals.id/index.php/IJWL/article/view/212>